

**A MEMORANDUM ON THE PROPER HUMAN SEXUAL RIGHTS AND
GHANAIAN FAMILY VALUES BILL 2021**

**SUBMITTED TO
THE COMMITTEE ON LEGAL, CONSTITUTIONAL AND PARLIAMENTARY
AFFAIRS, PARLIAMENT OF GHANA**

BY

[REDACTED] (CRAZINIST ARTIST)

T T O
crazinis artis studi

TO: The Honourable Chairman And Members, Committee on Legal, Constitutional, and Parliamentary Affairs, Parliament of Ghana

FROM: [REDACTED] (crazinisT artisT), Multidisciplinary Artist, Activist and the Director of perfocraZe International Artists Residency.

SUBJECT: Opposition to The Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021

DATE: October 8th, 2021.

I am writing this memorandum as a concerned citizen of Ghana, a "transvstar", transwoman, human right and cultural activist, multidisciplinary artist and the creative director of perfocraZe International Artists Residency.

This bill actually violates everything that I am, from my breath to my spirituality and, creative and cultural professionalism. The Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021 will adversely affect our contributions to the socio-political development, Ghanaian/African cultural identity advocacy and the economic growth of this country. On Tuesday 30th March 2021, the Ghanaian Time published the declaration of our president, His Excellency Nana Akufo Addo that Ghana is the safest space for international investment. Even though that claim is relatively untrue depending on the privileges of the investors, I want to state that this bill will go far much more to damage our safety and security for any form of investment including queer creative industries which is one of the biggest contributors to art and cultural investment across the globe.

Artists and arts are the seers, prophets and healers of our societies.

They help us reimagine the world around us and contribute to the future of our being. If we claim LGBTQIA+ is unafican, it is the failures of our predecessors who could not document and archive the pre colonial culture, art and traditions of the people of Africa intentionally or unintentionally or as a result of colonial censorship of our history. Similarly this bill will again cause and cost the future generations who will have no information on how queer people exist today if the bill is determined to silence artists, journalists, educators, advocates and professors who are today's archivers and historians of our culture.

Art should be democratic and should reflect all subject including gender and sexuality

Through art we are able to touch the most sensitive issues and political failures in ways that open liberal and democratic conversations on new policies or amendments. It is with no doubt that if such a bill is passed in Ghana we will gradually migrate into dictatorship, ‘zipping the lips’ of all Ghanaian citizens both home and abroad on issues that may be affecting us. Anti LGBTQIA+ bill is just an excuse to begin such a destructive, injurious and "retrogressive agenda" of seizing power, censoring and silencing the voices of the people.

Art and culture is a basic and fundamental spiritual need of every human society.

It reflects the challenges, progress, evolution and philosophical ideologies of specific cultural groups, identity, spirituality, politics and its economic growth. In Ghana, our traditional art history reveals several sculptures with 3 heads or more, 2/3 genitals, bearded heads with breasts and so on suggesting that our ancestral deities are non binary, two spirited and non conforming. Of course Christianity and colonialism has demonised our own art forms while they stole them into their museums that has been generating over several billions of dollars for the western economy. The constitutional denial of such freedom of expression is a total attempt to completely erase the entire history of the several generations and Ghana as a multicultural nation. It was similar damage that was caused by colonialism preventing the indigenous people from teaching the younger generations their traditions, creativity, religion, spirituality, philosophy and other forms of indigenous knowledge. Nevertheless they condemn indigenous cultures as demonic and satanic. It is therefore empathetic that as an independent country we would want to pass a new bill in affirmation of colonial demonisation of African traditions, sexuality, gender, ‘Blackness’, cultural research and creative interventions.

LGBTQIA+ and Queer creative have always been part of Africans

Lack of Knowledge we Ghanaians will perish killing ourselves... Ghana is bigger than us and itself with unique tribes, cultures, traditions, clans and families. Same-sex attractions; marriages and queer relationships have been with Africans and every human society since the beginning of humans until colonialism and western religious invasions. However, Art and the creative industries have always been vibrant ways to contribute to social changes, research and postcolonial discourses in our time. Most often the African continent with over thousands of ethnic languages has been reduced to a bilingual continent predominantly with English and French thereby simplifying Africa ‘geopolitically’ into a ‘one-man-village’. The people of waadabe also known as the Mbororo or Bororo encourage men to

wear elaborate make-up, feathers and other adornments (which may be considered here as crossdressing or transgendering) in performing the Yaake for suitors. It is a unique expression of gender fluidity, and subversion of heteronormativity and patriarchy. According to the research of Italo Signorini in the 1970s, the Nzema people of Nkelekazo have been practicing same-sex marriage far back before colonialism, men married men known as 'Agonwole agyale'. Orompoto, the First Female Alaafin of Oyo came to be popularly known as Ajiun, the custodian of the vagina that kills evil plots, her story is a very unique one that remains among the Oyo but we may have similar characters across other traditions if we invest into uncovering our own histories.

As a queer person, transvatar, activist and international creative professional, I have witnessed across the globe how queer creative individuals and groups are contributing to the economy of their countries, communities, cities, festivals and the world at large. From fashion through the visual arts to performance and theatre LGBTQIA+ persons have immensely and indiscriminately contributed to the vibrant global art scene and culture. But the constant abuse, harassment, threats and blackmail suffered by LGBTQIA+ persons in Ghana does not encourage queer models, singers, dancers, fashion designers and other queer creatives to explore their talents and potentials.

African Spirituality: Democracy, Cooperation, Tolerance, Hospitality And Love

This bill with all of its intentions will again wound our traditions as people of diversity, tolerance and love. It will destroy our indigenous spirituality and hospitality. I will say again and again that humanity begins from Africa, a place where when you fall, people will run to your rescue and try to revive you before thinking about your colour, tribe, gender, and so on. What will happen to us after this bill? First of all we must acknowledge that Africa is larger than we have been thought through the lens of Eurocentric anthropology and colonialism. We are people of unique traditions, rituals, spirituality and dynamic experiences even in the smallest tribes and clans on the continent. The idea that LGBTQIA+ is unafrikan is still a colonial misconception because what might be Ewe traditions may not be the same among the Ashantis, the Fantis, the Nzemas, the Gonjas, the Gas, the Dagaabas, just to name a few within Ghana (1 out of 54 unique countries with several hundreds of tribes in each). Ghana however, was built and born in the spiritual front and light of "unity in diversity" acknowledging that for our independence to be complete we must understand the differences of our unique and dynamic traditions that brought us together as a nation. The 'Funtunfunefu Denkyemfunefu' (Siamese crocodiles) an Adinkra symbol of the Akans expresses democracy and cooperation. It represents unity among different religions, gender, cultural tolerance and intercultural acceptance of one another.

I guess we may agree that for similar reasons of our diverse cultures, Ghana has not yet or could not achieve a singular local language as a national language. We believe and value every single traditional set that make up this country, but unfortunately lack of historical education on various ethnicities and tribes is 'flashing away' the history of minorities. This bill must not contribute to the pains, the agony and traumas of wounded Africa and its minority group.

Homophobia is a colonial Virus and a Western indoctrination.

Constant attempts during and after colonialism to erase African indigenous history is the reason we are here today debating whether or not such a 'hateful bill' should be passed. There has never been any logical argument for the validation of Homophobia on this continent, however, others may weakly reference the Bible, British constitution (unnatural carnal knowledge) and American Conservative ideologies on procreation as reason to kill or rape us. First of all, if we agree that Ghana's independence for the liberation for all does not make Ghana a Christian state then we need to respect and acknowledge all belief systems and non religious citizens as well. We should therefore not base a national constitution on any religious sentiment and doctrines. The church must be separated from the State. Secondly, even though the term unnatural carnal knowledge has nothing specifically to do with LGBTQIA+ persons some law interpreters have translated it in favour of homophobic propaganda. Nevertheless, Section 104 of the Criminal Code of Ghana (which was institutionalised by the colonial masters through the very lens of Eurocentric religious (Biblical) interpretations) is applicable to all citizens of Ghana regardless of their sexuality and gender orientation. If it criminalises unnatural carnal knowledge limiting sexual intercourse to 'solely' vaginal penetration, then we may all agree that about 90 % of Ghanaians if not all have already failed by engaging in oral sex, fisting, anal sex (even among heterosexuals), sex toys and vibrators that may even be medically recommended for some heterosexual couples etc. This explains that the bill is unnecessarily aggressive towards LGBTQIA+ persons without proper understanding of the terms and what they actually are.

Last but not least, procreation is a choice if not a health failure or biological complications regardless of all our sexualities. There are some heterosexual couples who may never give birth due to biological problems or medical factors. I don't think they have committed any crime for not procreating in any sense. On the other hand, if they desire to "own" babies there are several other ways they can afford, i.e. adoption, sperm donations/insemination and so on. Similarly same-sex relationships can own babies without necessarily having to conceive. Same-sex couples may also conceive and give birth if they desire just heterosexuals. There are transwomen and transmen here in Ghana who have their own

biological family and children. LGBTQIA+ persons do not stand against procreation. There are thousands of homeless and street children out there in the city centres but have no one to care for them. Is that the kind of family values we want to promote and uphold as a national pride? According the accounts on Female-husbandry, Queen Njinga (who rose to power over the Ndongo kingdom in 1624) married women who got pregnant and gave birth. Her history actually defeats the conservative assumption that LGBTQIA+ person prevents procreation. In 2005, anthropologists Robin Morgan and Saskia Wieringa have identified same-sex relationships among women in more than forty contemporary African cultures. We can find critical accounts of several same sex African relationships from books such as Male Daughters, Female Husbands: Gender and Sex in an African Society; Boy-wives and Female Husbands: Studies in African Homosexualities; Tommy boys, lesbian men and ancestral wives; Agɔnwɔle agyale: the marriage between two persons of the same sex among the Nzema of southwestern Ghana.

In conclusion, it will be the worst tragedy that will befall Ghana should this bill be passed. Many Ghanaians will use it as an excuse to harm both LGBTQIA+ persons and non LGBTQIA+ persons all in the name of ‘social cleansing’. It will be no different from the genocide during Hitler regime nor the Salem witch trials (in colonial Massachusetts, USA). It will send Ghana far back, and all that has been built by our ancestors who fought for independence, democracy and justice will be lost again in innocent bloodshed. It is rather very important to reinvest into African history covering creativity, spirituality, gender, sexuality and include African indigenous studies in Ghanaian curriculum where the younger generation will learn about their own history; pre-colonialism, colonialism and postcolonialism.

Thanks.

(crazinisT artisT)

October 8th, 2021.

References:

- Agonwole agyale : the marriage between two persons of the same sex among the Nzema of southwestern Ghana, https://www.persee.fr/doc/jafr_0037-9166_1973_num_43_2_1713
- <https://www.nps.gov/afbg/learn/historyculture/tanit.htm>
- Orompoto, the First Female Alaafin of Oyo:
<https://guardian.ng/life/orompoto-the-first-female-alaafin-of-oyo/>
- Queering History, Queering Africa
https://www.albany.edu/faculty/jhobson/middle_passages/queerafrica/essay.html
- Male Daughters, Female Husbands: Gender and Sex in an African Society, Ifi Amadiume
- Boy-wives and Female Husbands: Studies in African Homosexualities; Stephen O. Murray, Will Roscoe
- Tommy boys, lesbian men and ancestral wives, Ruth Morgan and Saskia Wieringa
- Gender, Democracy and Institutional Development in Africa, Njoki Nathani Wane